

Efficiency of Using Web-Technologies in Teaching Process

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ABSTRACT

The use of Internet technologies in the educational process has become a novelty in the last decade. Teachers in advanced training courses actively study work in virtual environments and develop methods for teaching various subjects. In educational process, information and Internet technologies are actively used. They are aimed at developing the creative potential of students, as well as at the formation of key competencies. The article deals with the issues based on describing the educational potential of web-technologies.

Keywords: web-technologies, educational process, virtual environments, mobility of educational process, virtual tours, interactive communication.

INTRODUCTION

The conveniences of using web technologies are explained by the fact that information can be arranged hierarchically and have direct access to each block. When gaps in knowledge are discovered, it is easy to return to the block that has not been carefully worked out. Detailing a large amount of information contributes to the qualitative assimilation of topics in the classroom. The main advantage is also that students are not tied to a specific computer. They save their data, tasks, developments on certain topics in the "cloud" and have access to information at any time. At school, at home, on vacation, having a smartphone, tablet, laptop or other mobile device with them, students are able to access the Internet, make

changes to personal data, create a work schedule, write down solutions to a problem, or perform other actions. There is an increase in mobility of both students and teachers. Presentation and transmission of information can occur in various forms. Participants in the educational process choose the method that suits them best. Making virtual tours, visualizing information, transferring educational and methodological material in different formats, interactive communication, announcing the results of work - all this is possible with the help of web technologies. The learning process involves communication between the student and the teacher. If in the traditional education system the teacher was the authority and source of knowledge for the student, now he is the coordinator in the big world of information. For communication during and after school hours, it is convenient to use chats, sending messages, e-mail, video calls. These resources provide the user with ample opportunities for the rapid exchange of views on a particular problem with an unlimited number of interested parties. Being in the process of independent work on the study of a topic in a certain area, the student can ask a question, present his point of view, organize a discussion on the problem of interest.

DISCUSSIONS

This contributes to the development of communication skills, the ability to conduct a dialogue, defend one's own opinion, and objectively evaluate the interlocutor's conclusions on the topic. To present the results of research activities or exchange of experience, it is effective to organize teleconferences. They contribute to the solution of complex educational tasks: increasing the general educational level of students in a specific subject area, developing communication and research skills. Storage and processing of various types of information is another of the didactic possibilities of web technologies.

The most significant resources that provide an opportunity to collect information, perform research tasks and projects are Internet search engines and electronic libraries of various levels. Systematization of the collected information is possible with the help of databases created on the basis of web 2.0 technology. The teacher, students can structure, process, edit and supplement everything that they have stored in their virtual personal account.

The design of the educational process occurs due to the many opportunities provided by Internet technologies. For example, the organization of large electronic encyclopedias, teleconferences, joint research work of students, teachers and even parents, access to world knowledge bases. Self-education, self-development in the course of the modern lesson are one of the main directions. Due to web-services and other cloud technologies, the process of independent work of the student becomes interesting, colorful.

Self-assessment occurs after presenting your results to a teacher, parents, or classmates. Telling the course of his work, the student himself analyzes what he did. Often communication and demonstration is organized through the use of online services, social networks. After the discussion, there is a re-analysis and correction of errors, if any. With the help of web technologies, the teacher has the ability to create, edit and place their educational web resources, send them to students, and store them on the Internet. Through computers that are connected to a single educational space, you can run training programs, simulators. The interactivity of this innovation is very high due to multimedia support and prompt feedback. The organization of distance learning becomes available. Informing about upcoming events, conferences and competitions is a problem for many educational institutions. Whiteboard announcements or talking to teachers about upcoming classroom events are not always effective.

Web-services come to the rescue, with the help of which advertisements are colorfully drawn up, information tapes are compiled, animated videos are created. Students pay attention to such announcements, which are designed in the form of advertisements, learn information, and then take part in activities, both creative and scientific.

The use of web-technologies in the educational process significantly activates learners in the study of subjects, contributes to the expansion and deepening of students' knowledge, the effective development of research and project work methods. Intellectual and creative initiative, the educational and cognitive interest of students and the development of a communication culture help them achieve high results. Figure 1.3 shows a diagram of the use of web technologies in the educational process. Contributing to the expansion of many opportunities for students, revealing talents, increasing interest in learning and achieving results leads to an improvement in the educational process.

The use of new technologies, the active use of the latest developments in the educational process, the high academic performance of students raises the status of the school. The use of web technologies in the lessons at school will change the approach to teaching subjects. The educational environment built with the help of the Internet significantly changes the positions of the participants in the educational process, and creates the prerequisites for the transition of the information development of the student to a qualitatively new level.

The active development of cloud technologies in all areas makes it possible to form a "cloud toolkit" for a modern teacher. The structure of the "cloud toolkit" of a school teacher may include such blocks as general-purpose cloud services, account aggregators, cloud office applications, cloud presentations, graphic cloud services, specialized cloud services [4]. General-purpose cloud services can be

used as a tool for data exchange, content storage, and an auxiliary pedagogical resource. This block includes search engines, image hosting, - audio, - video files. Any web service requires authorized access. Some of them support access using accounts of popular social and email resources.

In this case, it is useful to use an account aggregator to consolidate from a large number of sites and combine them into one universal one. An example of this type of web service is Loginza, which is an OpenId 2.0 account provider. The advantage of such an aggregator is that you can visit many sites under one account, a high level of security is provided, the ability to design a personal profile (business card). Cloud office applications are replacing popular office suites such as MS Office and OpenOffice. There are cloud counterparts to these software products that implement almost all functions and are free. CrocoDoc service - a service in which joint editing of documents is possible. The most common office formats, graphics, PDF format, automatic download of a page screenshot, work in a joint editing mode with another user - all this is possible in this service. Google Docs (Google Docs) is a free online service formed as a result of the merger of Writely and Google Spreadsheets. Its capabilities exceed the potential of CrocoDoc. Google Docs includes a text and spreadsheet editor, a service for creating presentations, cloud storage, and file sharing. There are also many other web services for working with text, from notepads for notes to a powerful word processor. For example, DocMe, Ontext (publishing texts), PrivNote (online notepad for quick notes), SkyDrive. The block of cloud presentations includes innovative web services in which it is possible to create non-linear presentations. is a web application that provides services such as creating, managing and distributing a presentation. Possibility of uploading video, graphics, tables, pictures to the service. Data can be collected with simple online actions..com is a service

that completely surpasses the power of PowerPoint. Create presentations in a non-linear way.

On the boundless canvas, you can upload pictures, video / audio materials, type text with a choice of the style and format you like. The result is a solid presentation map that can be downloaded to your computer and played using a Flash player. The material is depicted as a whole picture, which makes it easy to perceive information and work with it. It is possible to work in a collective mode. Prezi.com is available as a desktop and native app that can be downloaded from AppStory and Play Market. Show is an online service of the Zoho family, very close and similar to Google Docs web applications. Zoho Show wins in competition in many areas: managing various documents, online collaboration, the ability to post a presentation on a website. - a social service for hosting presentations.

Allows us to convert desktop PowerPoint presentations and play also with Flash player. This Computer graphics is now used by all participants in the educational process, so graphic cloud services have also been created. Pixlr.com is the ideal solution to replace the Photoshop editor and Gimp. It includes such services as: Pixlr Editor (full-featured graphics editor, support for several languages, work with high quality images, supports many functions from the expensive Photoshop program), Pixlr Express (fast image processing, contains basic functions such as changing image resolution , cropping, effects, shadows), Pixlr-o-matic (the ability to work with bitmaps using nested templates), Pixlr imm.io (hosting for graphic files), Pixlr Grabber (a browser add-on that "grabs" an image from a web pages viewed by the user). This series of online services has native versions. The Flash-Gear Drawing service is designed to create drawings that are saved on a server with the ability to copy to a local computer. Here is a

large gallery of built-in drawings, where several users can draw at once. The service belongs to the Flash-Gear collection. Live share photo service allows you to create photo albums. In this environment, you can exchange comments, links, use the privacy function. In the classroom, Live share should be used for projects, research, publishing, and school work. Specialized cloud services reflect the specifics of a particular subject. Examples are virtual whiteboards, timelines, mapping services, translators, mind maps, and more [5]. Let's look at examples of a virtual whiteboard for group work.

The Concept board service provides teamwork for creating brief notes and ideas, the ability to post images and documents, annotate and communicate in the form of a conference. The service supports Cyrillic and is available only after registration. The ability to save intermediate options for the design of the board [1]. Scrumblr.com is a great service for organizing group, real-time collaboration. The functionality of this application is similar to that of the Concept board. The difference is that the work does not require registration. It is fast, light and simple tool.vice is intended for the storage and use of material, both personal and shared.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, Web technologies represent a new way of organizing the educational process and offer an alternative to traditional methods of organizing the educational process, creating an opportunity for personal learning, collective teaching and interactive classes. The main advantage of using cloud technologies in education is not only to reduce the cost of acquiring the necessary software, to improve the efficiency and quality of the educational process, but also to prepare pupils and students for life in the modern information society.

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